

Reactions of 2-imino-3-aryl-4-phenyl-4-thiazolines with 2-cyanopyrazine and 4-cyanopyridine : difference in reactivity

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Abstract : The kinetics of the reactions of 2-imino-3-aryl-4-phenyl-4-thiazolines (2-ITZ, 3a-e) with 2-cyanopyrazine (2-CPZ, 1) and 4-cyanopyridine (4-CPY, 2) have been carried out in methanol at various temperatures. Results show that 2-ITZ derivatives (3a-e) reacted faster and more readily at ambient temperature with 2-CPZ than with 4-CPY. 2-CPZ readily reacted with methanol forming an amidate ester, while 4-CPY did not. The amidate ester was prone to nucleophilic substitution (OMe being a good leaving group). Slower reaction rate was observed for the reactions of 2-CPZ with 2-ITZ and its derivatives in THF. On the other hand 4-CPY did not react with 2-ITZ derivatives even under extreme conditions in THF. The order of reactivity of various substituents both in MeOH and in THF is : *p*-OMe > *o*-OMe > *p*-CH₃ > *o*-CH₃ > H. The isokinetic temperatures, T_{iso} for the reactions of 2-ITZ with 2-CPZ and 4-CPY in MeOH were 352.6 K and 438.3 K respectively.

Keywords : Heterocyclic compounds, thiazolines, cyanopyrazine.

Due to potential anti HIV, antibacterial and antifungal activities of a variety of heterocyclic compounds¹⁻⁵ containing nitrogen or sulphur, attempts were made to enlarge the scope and hence 2-cyanopyrazine (2-CPZ, 1) and 4-cyanopyridine (4-CPY, 2) were reacted with variously substituted 2-imino-3-aryl-4-phenyl-4-thiazolines (2-ITZ, 3a-e) to obtain highly potential heterocyclic compounds as depicted in Scheme 1.

Study on solvent effect is one of the most useful methods to obtain information on the mechanism of organic reactions⁶.

Hydrogen bond acceptor and hydrogen bond donor abilities⁷⁻¹¹ of solvents affect aromatic nucleophilic substitution reactions (ANS). The gross mechanism of ANS reactions is now well established for primary and secondary amines acting as nucleophiles¹². Most of the kinetic studies devoted to ANS reactions with amines indicate that the occurrence and efficiency of base catalysis depend on the nature of the amine, the nucleofuge and the solvent. Base catalysis is generally observed in those cases where the leaving group (nucleofuge) is reluctant to depart and is facilitated by the use of a strong base (for example, a secondary amine) in a less polar medium¹³⁻¹⁷. These studies reflect the extensive and complex nature of interaction of the substrate and/or the intermediate with the solvent molecules. To see the ef-

Scheme 1

fect of solvent polarity on the reactions of 2-ITZ with 2-CPZ, methanol (dielectric const. 33) and THF (dielectric const. 7.5) widely differing in polarity were used. The

Table 1. Values of pseudo-first order rate constant (k_0) and second order rate constant (k_A) for the reactions of 2-CPZ with 2-imino-3-aryl-4-phenyl-4-thiazoline (2-ITZ) derivatives in MeOH and THF

[2-CPZ] = 1.98×10^{-4} mol/dm³ and [2-ITZ] = $20-60 \times 10^{-4}$ mol/dm³

Str. no.	Nu.	$10^{-4} k_0 \text{ min}^{-1}, 299 \text{ K}$					$10^{-4} k_A \text{ min}^{-1}$		
		$(k_A, \text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1})$					$(k_A, \text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1})$		
MeOH									
4a	3-Phenyl	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	307 K	315 K	323 K
		8.4 (0.42)	15.1 (0.51)	21.7 (0.54)	27.3 (0.55)	30.2 (0.50)	73.6 (1.47)	121 (2.42)	163.5 (3.27)
4b	3-(<i>o</i> -Tolyl)	11 (0.55)	19.7 (0.66)	25.1 (0.63)	31.3 (0.63)	37 (0.62)	74.3 (1.49)	116 (2.32)	159 (3.18)
		4c	3-(<i>p</i> -Tolyl)	10.8 (0.54)	20.9 (0.7)	28 (0.7)	37 (0.74)	42 (0.7)	98.3 (1.96)
4d	3-(<i>o</i> -Anisyl)			17.5 (0.88)	31.3 (1.05)	46.7 (1.17)	61 (1.22)	84 (1.40)	128 (2.56)
		4e	3-(<i>p</i> -Anisyl)	18.6 (0.94)	38.4 (1.05)	46.3 (1.16)	67 (1.34)	89 (1.49)	143 (2.86)
THF									
4a	3-Phenyl	0.70 (0.035)	1.46 (0.049)	2.01 (0.05)	3.41 (0.068)	3.81 (0.063)	12.1 (0.242)	19.9 (0.39)	27.2 (0.54)
		4b	3-(<i>o</i> -Tolyl)	0.78 (0.039)	1.39 (0.046)	1.88 (0.047)	2.38 (0.048)	2.80 (0.046)	8.99 (0.179)
4c	3-(<i>p</i> -Tolyl)			1.34 (0.067)	2.10 (0.072)	3.16 (0.079)	3.89 (0.078)	5.22 (0.087)	12.97 (0.26)
		4d	3-(<i>o</i> -Anisyl)	2.80 (0.142)	4.20 (0.14)	5.70 (0.143)	7.30 (0.146)	9.20 (0.153)	18.2 (0.36)
4e	3-(<i>p</i> -Anisyl)			4.90 (0.243)	8.00 (0.266)	10.89 (0.272)	14.01 (0.28)	16.28 (0.271)	40.9 (0.818)

reactions of 2-ITZ with 2-CPZ were studied both in MeOH and THF and those with 4-CPY in MeOH only due to very slow reaction of 4-CPY in THF. It is of interest to compare the results of kinetic studies of 2-CPZ and 4-CPY with 2-ITZ in MeOH and THF and examine the effect of the presence of the second hetero atom in the same aromatic ring.

Experimental

Organic solvents used were of high purity unless otherwise cited. 2-Imino-3-aryl-4-phenyl-4-thiazolines (**3a-e**) were prepared¹⁸ by the condensation of phenacyl thiocyanate with amine hydrochlorides. 2-Cyanopyrazine (**1**) or 4-cyanopyridine (**2**), (1 mmol) dissolved in methanol (50 mL) was treated with 2-imino-3-aryl-4-phenyl-4-thiazoline (1 mmol) and heated under reflux for 16 h and then solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The solid residue left behind was purified by crystallization to obtain pure products **4a-e** and **5a-e**. The physical constants and spectral data were found to be the same as

observed in our earlier work¹. The product (**6**) of the reactions of 2-CPZ with methanol was isolated (m.p. 103 °C). ¹H NMR spectrum of (**6**) was recorded (300 MHz, CDCl₃) and showed signals at δ 4.05 (3H, s, OCH₃), 8.62–8.69 (2H, d, pyrazine protons), 9.09 (1H, s, pyrazine proton), 9.22 (1H, s, NH exch).

Kinetic procedure : The kinetics of the reactions were followed using a Shimadzu UV-1601 UV-Vis spectrophotometer operating in both spectral and kinetic modes. The spectrophotometer was coupled to a PC that allowed absorbance measurement vs time each 20-second and the multi cell holder was thermostated to temperature ± 0.1 °C, using a 240 A-Shimadzu thermostat. The reactions were followed at 267 nm, the λ_{max} of the product, which was found to be nearly the same in all the solvents used for kinetic studies. The λ_{max} of the product and its absorbance at infinite reaction time were constant with the corresponding authentic sample within $\pm 3-5\%$. Since the reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions, these obeyed the first order kinetic eq. (1).

$$k_0 t = 2.303 \log a/(a-x) \quad (1)$$

where (a) is the initial concentration of the substrate, (x) is the concentration of the product at time (t) and k_0 is the pseudo-first order rate constant; (a) and ($a-x$) were determined in terms of $A_\infty - A_0$ and $A_\infty - A_t$ where A_∞ , A_t and A_0 are the absorbances at infinity, t and zero time, respectively. The equation can be simplified to eq. (2).

$$\log (A_\infty - A_t) = -k_0 t/2.303 + \log (A_\infty - A_0) \quad (2)$$

k_0 values were calculated numerically in EXCEL from the linear plots of $1 + \log (A_\infty - A_t)$ versus time and the second order rate constants, k_A , were obtained by dividing k_0 by the nucleophile concentration [B]. Duplicate kinetic runs with correlation coefficients of $R > 0.997$ were accepted.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectra of all the compounds under experimental conditions show no appreciable effect on λ_{\max} with change in the structure of nucleophile or solvent. The values of pseudo-first order rate constant k_0 and second order rate constant k_A ($k_A = k_0/[\text{Nu}]$) for the reactions of 2-ITZ (3a-e) with (1) in MeOH, THF and with (2) in MeOH only in five different concentrations of 2-ITZ derivatives, $[20-60 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol/dm}^3]$ are reported in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The temperature effect on the values of k_0 at $[2\text{-ITZ}] = 50 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol/dm}^3$ are also given in Tables 1 and 2.

From Tables 1 and 2, it is obvious that 2-ITZ derivatives react at a faster rate with 2-CPZ than with 4-CPY. Also it is clear from the tables that 2-CPZ undergoes

nucleophilic substitution more readily at ambient temperatures than 4-CPY. The latter reacts at a higher temperature, e.g. 50 °C. The following points support the above observation.

(i) It was found that 2-CPZ reacted with MeOH quite readily forming the amidate ester (6), following the reaction :

Scheme 2

This amidate ester undergoes nucleophilic substitution (OMe being a good leaving group) to give the final products 4a-e, at a faster rate than 4-CPY, which did not react with MeOH.

(ii) A slower reaction rate was observed for the reactions of 2-CPZ (1) with 2-ITZ derivatives 3a-b in THF (products 4a-e). On the other hand 4-CPY (2) did not react with 2-ITZ to give the products 5a-e when solvent was THF under normal conditions, and reacted only at a high temperature.

(iii) Another evidence of interest is that 2-CPZ reacts at a rate faster than 4-CPY. A comparison of the structures of 2-CPZ and 4-CPY reveals that N-1 in 2-CPZ is of special importance and plays a prominent role. Being more electronegative than carbon, N-1 of 2-CPZ exerts

Table 2. Values of pseudo-first order rate constant (k_0) and second order rate constant (k_A) for the reactions of 4-CPY with 2-imino-3-aryl-4-phenyl-4-thiazoline (2-ITZ) derivatives in MeOH

Str. no.	Nu.	$[4\text{-CPY}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol/dm}^3$ and $[2\text{-ITZ}] = 20-60 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol/dm}^3$					$10^{-4} k_0 \text{ min}^{-1}$		
		$10^{-4} k_0 \text{ min}^{-1}, 299 \text{ K}$					$(k_A, \text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1})$		
		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	303 K	309 K	315 K
5a	3-Phenyl	3.22	4.83	5.98	7.60	8.06	1.00	2.10	3.45
		(0.161)	(0.161)	(0.149)	(0.152)	(0.134)	(0.22)	(0.042)	(0.07)
5b	3-(<i>o</i> -Tolyl)	2.99	9.20	14.0	20.7	26.4	3.45	5.98	10.5
		(0.149)	(0.307)	(0.351)	(0.414)	(0.441)	(0.069)	(0.12)	(0.21)
5c	3-(<i>p</i> -Tolyl)	8.00	11.9	17.5	27.8	35.6	5.06	8.50	14.7
		(0.403)	(0.399)	(0.437)	(0.557)	(0.594)	(0.10)	(0.17)	(0.29)
5d	3-(<i>o</i> -Anisyl)	12.2	19.5	26.9	36.6	46.7	7.10	11.2	20.0
		(0.61)	(0.65)	(0.67)	(0.73)	(0.78)	(0.14)	(0.22)	(0.40)
5e	3-(<i>p</i> -Anisyl)	25.3	35.2	58.9	74.8	106.8	18.4	28.3	44.9
		(1.27)	(1.17)	(1.47)	(1.5)	(1.78)	(0.36)	(0.56)	(0.90)

its electron-withdrawing inductive effect and makes the carbon atom of the nitrile group more electron-deficient and hence more prone to nucleophilic attack at ambient temperatures. It reacted readily with methanol to form an amidate ester. This enhanced electrophilicity on the nitrile carbon atom is absent in 4-CPY and hence less prone to nucleophilic attack. It did not react with methanol at ambient temperature. The role of second hetero atom in the ring is quite evident.

(iv) Also in the reactions of both the substrates (2-CPZ and 4-CPY), nucleophilic aromatic substitution of the cyano group has not been observed.

From Tables 1–2, it is seen that k_0 (pseudo-first order rate constant) increases with increase in nucleophile concentration. The values of second order rate constants were higher in MeOH than in THF under the same conditions. This is attributable to higher E_T^N (normalized polarity parameters) value of MeOH (0.762), than that of THF (0.207). It facilitated more solvation of the charged intermediate complex through H-bonding in MeOH than in THF leading to fast proton expulsion to give the product. Generation of such an intermediate species (T^\pm) stabilized by H-bonding in the reactions of **6** with 2-ITZ and of **2** with 2-ITZ leading to the formation of **4** and **5** respectively, are shown in Schemes 3 and 4.

Scheme 3

The hydrogen bond formation helps in stabilizing the intermediate.

Scheme 4

A significant acceleration in the reaction rate occurred with increasing nucleophile concentration for the formation of compounds **4d** and **4e** in MeOH and THF and **4b-e** in MeOH. This indicates that nucleophilic substitution reaction is catalyzed by base in MeOH. It seems that the formation of dipolar intermediate from the reactants is not the rate determining step. Large HBD ability { $DN = 19$ and $E_T(30) = 55.4$ } of MeOH effectively assists in proton detachment from the intermediate that is rate limiting¹⁹.

From Tables 1 and 2 it is evident that changing substituent (on nucleophile moiety) from H to OCH₃, about three fold increase in the rate occurs in the case of 2-CPZ in both MeOH and THF, while more than ten fold increase in the rate occurs in the case of 4-CPY. This indicates that the carbon atom of nitrile group of the 2-CPZ molecules is well activated for nucleophilic attack.

In general, the order of reactivity of various substituents in MeOH and THF for both 2-CPZ and 4-CPY are : p -MeO > o -MeO > p -CH₃ > o -CH₃ > H. This observation is in agreement with the expected enhancement of nucleophilicity of the imino group by electron donating

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters and frequency factors for the reactions of 2-CPZ with 2-ITZ derivatives in MeOH

Compd.	E_a (kJ/mol)	$\log A$ (min ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ/mol)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (J/mol K)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ/mol)
4a	59.19	7.83	78.02 ± 0.56	69.12 ± 1.29	56.52 ± 0.06
4b	53.63	6.90	77.98 ± 0.67	86.00 ± 1.00	50.97 ± 0.06
4c	53.56	6.68	77.43 ± 0.69	85.00 ± 1.30	50.91 ± 0.06
4d	44.34	5.57	76.65 ± 0.87	112 ± 0.93	41.7 ± 0.06
4e	47.77	6.21	76.3 ± 0.77	100 ± 0.85	45.13 ± 0.06

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters and frequency factors for the reactions of 2-CPZ with 2-ITZ derivatives in THF

Compd.	E_a (kJ/mol)	$\log A$ (min ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ/mol)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (J/mol K)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ/mol)
4a	68.20	8.5	83.38 ± 0.59	57.98 ± 1.45	65.35 ± 0.06
4b	67.48	8.26	83.74 ± 0.63	60.88 ± 1.96	64.80 ± 0.06
4c	64.89	8.00	82.74 ± 0.62	65.84 ± 1.60	62.21 ± 0.06
4d	58.23	7.08	81.52 ± 0.65	83.46 ± 1.20	55.57 ± 0.06
4e	59.69	6.64	79.67 ± 0.61	72.80 ± 1.40	57.03 ± 0.06

Table 5. Thermodynamic parameters and frequency factors for the reactions of 2-CPZ with 2-ITZ derivatives in MeOH

Compd.	E_a (kJ/mol)	$\log A$ (min ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ/mol)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (J/mol K)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ/mol)
5a	79.43	6.68	87.16 ± 0.17	33.62 ± 0.21	76.66 ± 0.09
5b	71.51	8.85	84.30 ± 0.22	49.48 ± 0.14	68.86 ± 0.08
5c	68.08	8.43	83.61 ± 0.37	57.64 ± 0.15	65.61 ± 0.28
5d	66.16	8.24	82.64 ± 0.27	61.30 ± 0.28	63.50 ± 0.07
5e	56.18	6.94	80.44 ± 0.46	86.12 ± 0.15	53.54 ± 0.07

effect, which helped in stabilizing the intermediate complex $T^{\pm 20,21}$. A good agreement with the Arrhenius relationship for the reactions of 2-CPZ in MeOH, THF and for 4-CPY in MeOH was observed. The correlation²² coefficients R^2 for the reactions of 2-CPZ in MeOH and THF are in the range ($R^2 = 0.9296$ to 0.9629) and ($R^2 = 0.9027$ to 0.952) respectively. This indicates that the intermediate complex contains H-bonded species, which is affected by temperature increase in support of solvation of the intermediate complex. An excellent relationship was found in the case of the reaction of 4-CPY, ($R^2 > 0.9991$).

The various thermodynamic parameters²³⁻²⁷ are shown in Tables 3-5. In all the cases large negative values of entropy of activation were obtained, indicating that the intermediate complex is highly charged and crowded.

From Tables 3 and 4 it is observed that for the reactions of 2-CPZ, only ΔH^\ddagger (enthalpy of activation) and ΔS^\ddagger (entropy of activation) are significantly affected by solvent composition, but ΔG^\ddagger (free energy of activation)

was nearly 77 kJ/mol and 82 kJ/mol for the reactions in MeOH and THF respectively, demonstrating enthalpy-entropy compensation effect²⁸.

As $\Delta G^\ddagger = \Delta H^\ddagger - T\Delta S^\ddagger$, similar changes in magnitude and sign of ΔH^\ddagger and $T\Delta S^\ddagger$ cancel ΔG^\ddagger totally or partially. The compensation effect is operating when ΔG^\ddagger is constant for a reaction series and ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger vary significantly (Tables 3 and 4). The slope of the plot ΔS^\ddagger versus ΔH^\ddagger (the isokinetic temperature), T_{iso} was found to be 352.6 K and 422 K for the reactions of 2-ITZ with 2-CPZ in MeOH and THF respectively. The corresponding value for the reactions with 4-CPY in MeOH was 438.3 K. This evidence is in support of the claim that a single mechanism is in operation for a solvent series.

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